

DESIGN, USAGE AND SAFETY ASPECTS FOR TUBULAR SPECIMENS FOR MATERIALS QUALIFICATION WITH PRESSURISED HYDROGEN

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Typically, autoclaves are used to characterise materials under a hydrogen atmosphere. Those systems are expensive in installation and usage due to the high safety requirements. A cost efficient and reliable alternative without the need of explosive protection might be the tubular specimen technique. In this technique a small diameter axial hole is machined in the centre of the specimen, which is pressurised with gas. Comparing the results of specimens filled with pressurised hydrogen and, for reference with ambient air or pressurised nitrogen allows to conclude for the effect of hydrogen on material properties. The advantage of the tubular specimen technique is the very low volume of the explosive gas, compared to conventional autoclaves. This reduces safety risks and allows the implementation in existing testing machines with low efforts. This paper describes in detail the setup of a tubular specimen test system for tensile tests, addresses safety aspects and shows exemplary results.

Keywords: Hydrogen Embrittlement, Tubular Specimen, Pressurised Hydrogen, Materials Characterisation

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, hydrogen is being considered as a possible storage and transportation solution for renewable energy from sources such as wind and solar power. Pressurised hydrogen can be used in various ways, such as in gas turbines to produce electricity, as a starting product in chemical plants, or in fuel cells to power ships and airplanes. To ensure the safe and reliable use of these products, material properties are needed for the design process. Materials qualification under pressurised hydrogen atmosphere is typically performed using autoclaves attached to conventional test rigs. The advantage of autoclaves is that tests, such as tensile tests, fatigue tests, or fracture mechanics tests, can be conducted according to international ISO or ASTM standards [1, 2]. However, the drawback of autoclaves is that the pressure vessel is around the specimen, leading to high investment costs due to the big size of the pressure vessel and for safety issues with explosion protection. Furthermore, certain temperature ranges above 300°C or below -100°C are very difficult or even impossible to achieve with autoclaves, although temperatures above 300°C are normal operating temperatures for internal combustion engines.

One alternative is the use of tubular specimens, which are tube-like specimens filled on the inside with pressurised hydrogen. The idea dates back to the 1970s and 1980s [3–5], and today, a standard for tensile testing of tubular specimens is being prepared by ISO/TC 164/SC 1/WG 9. The obvious advantage of tubular specimens is the lower volume, which drastically reduces the amount of hydrogen to a few litres even at high pressures, reducing the risk of explosion. Furthermore, it is possible to use induction heating or a climate chamber for high or low temperatures. However, there are some drawbacks, such as specimen production and the question of how results achieved on

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tubular specimens compete with conventional specimens tested in an autoclave. This paper describes the setup of a tubular test system, compares the safety aspects to autoclaves, shows results for tensile tests, and addresses the current scientific questions regarding the use of tubular specimens for tensile tests.

TEST SETUP FOR TUBULAR SPECIMEN

Tubular specimens resemble conventional specimens, but with an axially centred longitudinal hole. In Figure 1 (upper) a picture and (lower) a technical drawing of a tubular tensile test specimen are shown.

FIGURE 1 Picture (upper) and technical drawing (lower) of a tubular specimen for tensile testing.

There are some methods to develop the longitudinal hole. One of them is deep hole drilling. Special drills are used for this purpose, which have channels in the centre for lubricant transport through the drill to the cutting tip. This ensures good lubrication and cooling, and chips are transported away by the returning lubricant. Better lathes are required for this, with sufficient pumping power for lubricant transport. Normal lathes with pressure up to 40 bar are not sufficient, better results are achieved by using at least 80 bar. Additionally, the lathes often have stabilisers for the drills to prevent the long drills from breaking. Although the surface quality of this method is better than that of ordinary drill presses, polished surfaces have a surface roughness that is approximately 10 times lower.

As an example, surface roughness measurements on the inner and outer surface of a tubular specimen made of Inconel 718 are shown in Table 1. The results comparing tubular specimens and conventional specimens, shown later in the document, indicate that the surface quality is acceptable for tensile testing. However, it is not under all circumstances sufficient for fatigue tests, for which normally polished surfaces are used. Therefore, methods to optimise the inner surface quality and understand its effect on fatigue tests remain a topic of research and engineering.

TABLE 1 Inner and outer roughness of a tubular specimens of Inconel 718.

Position	Rz	Ra	Picture
Inner Surface by deep hole drilling	1.32	0.23	
Outer Surface after polishing	0.26	0.05	

In the following the setup is described. At both ends of the specimen, threads are present to attach the fixture plates, as depicted in Figure 2a. To enable a backlash-free connection, a nut is used. On the very ends, a double ferrule connects the tubes and valves for the hydrogen supply, as shown in Figure 2b. This transportable system, comprising the specimen, fixture, and hydrogen connection, is taken to the gas station for hydrogen filling. This allows the hydrogen usage in a running test to be limited to a maximum pressure-volume product of less than 2 litres. After filling, the transportable system is mounted to the load rig, as shown in Figure 3a and 3b. On the outside of the fixture there are alignments fitting to the counterpart in the test rig to achieve a good alignment.

Since there is no hydrogen supply attached during a running test, leakage is critical for the success of the test. For this reason, membrane valves or needle valves with very low leakage are used. For slow strain tensile tests, running for about half a day, the pressure loss by leakage is less than 1% of the starting pressure. In fatigue tests conducted over several days, the pressure loss is even lower.

The reason for the higher pressure loss in tensile test is assumed to be the volume increase due to plastic deformation in a tensile test.

FIGURE 2 a) Specimen connected to the movable fixture and the tubes of hydrogen supply. b) Whole set of movable parts.

FIGURE 3 a) Test system with installed tubular specimen. b) Magnification of the specimen installed to the test system.

HEATING, COOLING AND SAFETY ASPECTS

Autoclaves used for testing conventional, normal-sized specimens in fatigue or tensile tests under pressurised hydrogen typically have an inner gross volume of a few litres. The net volume can be reduced by filling bodies, but there is a practical lower limit of approximately 0.5 litre as space is required for measurement devices and movement of the fixture, specimen, and drive shaft. With an inner pressure of 200 bars, this results in a hydrogen volume of 100 litres. Additionally, there is a permanent leakage at the gaskets sealing the drive shaft against the body of the autoclave. The explosive protection of the autoclave should therefore control both dangers of hydrogen release: (i) the permanent leakage and (ii) a possible fracturing gasket. In contrast, the tubular specimen has a pressure-volume product of less than 2 litres for pressures up to 400 bars and there is very little leakage. However, the gas is released at the end of the test by the fracture of the specimen, and the explosive protection needs to be adjusted to this danger. Normal-sized laboratory rooms often have a minimum cross-section of at least 5 m by 5 m and a ceiling height of 2.4 m, resulting in a volume

of 60,000 litres. The resulting mean hydrogen concentration in this size of a room at fracture is far below the lower explosive limit of about 4% of hydrogen in air. More critical is the short-time concentration upon fracture, which will be close to the point of fracture in a range inside the explosive concentration. For the shown test system, the hydrogen concentration was, assuming that hydrogen moves upward as it is lighter as air, measured upon fracture at 0.5m above the point of fracture and on the ceiling of laboratory room of earlier mentioned size. The measured hydrogen concentration of about 0.5% at the 0.5m position is below the lower explosive limit. On the ceiling, the hydrogen concentration was in the ppm-range. Five minutes after the fracture, no hydrogen was detectable in the room. Nevertheless, molecular hydrogen does not react with the oxygen in air without the starting energy. As a result, hydrogen could accumulate over days. This can be prevented by a ventilation system. Still, tubular specimens generally have lower safety concerns for explosive protection, but national explosive protection requirements must be respected in any case. For the shown test system, beside the limitation for a maximum pressure-volume product of 2 litres, no further explosive protection was used.

Main advantages of tubular specimens in comparison to autoclaves are easier heating and cooling, compare Figure 4. In Figure 4a, the tubular specimen technique is shown in combination with an induction coil for temperatures up to 800 °C. The coil is open at the front to allow the installation of the hydrogen-filled specimen, including the hydrogen connectors. The temperature distribution is fine for the short measuring area of fatigue specimens but is insufficient for tensile tests, which is intrinsic for most induction heating systems. As tests end with a fracture, there is a risk of ignition of the escaping gas above the ignition temperature, resulting in a darting flame. For the shown setup, a darting flame was acceptable as there were no combustible parts close to the specimen, namely about 1m in each direction, and the strictly limited hydrogen in the specimen. Risk assessment is always situation-dependent and must be individually conducted for each setup.

Figure 4b shows a liquid bath installed around the specimen. The hydrogen is contained within the specimen, and the liquid on the outside can be used for heating and cooling. In the depicted image, the bath was filled with liquid nitrogen for tensile and fatigue tests at 77 K. When this system is in use, a ventilation system and an oxygen gas alarm are employed in the laboratory for the safety of personnel due to the low oxygen concentration in the air caused by the evaporation of nitrogen.

Using a temperature chamber for the tubular specimens enables testing across a wide range of application-relevant temperatures, as demonstrated in Figure 4c. The temperature chamber depicted in the figure is equipped with a fan on the backside to circulate internal gas, a hole for injecting liquid nitrogen to achieve cooling, and electrical heating rods. The drive shaft of the fan is going through a very thin hole to prevent hot or cold gases coming from the chamber entering and damaging the power drive. At low temperatures conducted by injecting liquid nitrogen explosive atmospheres are not a concern as there is already mainly inert nitrogen. Heating is more critical as the heating rods reach temperatures far above the ignition temperatures of hydrogen. As a solution constant nitrogen flushing can be used to prevent explosive atmospheres. It helps that there is no constant hydrogen supply on the setup and the amount of hydrogen in the specimen is limited.

All three test systems have been or are currently being used on a daily basis for months without any safety concerns. The only exception is the setup with the temperature chamber, which is relatively new and has only been used for exemplar tests so far.

FIGURE 4 a) Test system with tubular specimen and induction heating for isothermal fatigue testing. b) Test system for tubular specimen and a liquid nitrogen cooling bath for tensile and fatigue tests at 77 K. c) Setup with a chamber for temperature-controlled isothermal tensile and fatigue tests between -80 °C and +200 °C.

However, the shown risk assessment and explosive protection solutions are specific solutions for the three shown test systems and mentioned exemplarily. It is highly recommended to conduct a comprehensive risk analysis and develop an individual explosive protection solution in accordance with national safety and explosive protection regulations for each unique setup.

EXEMPLARY TENSILE TEST RESULTS ACHIEVED WITH TUBULAR SPECIMENS

Tensile tests were conducted on specimens extracted from used pipeline of the vintage ferritic steel StE360. The chemical composition is given in Table 2. StE360 is a plain carbon steel with slightly increased manganese content and the similar available material nowadays is the API 5L X52.

TABLE 2 Chemical composition of steel StE360.

Element	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Cu	Fe
Weight-%	0.148	0.41	1.16	0.015	0.014	0.03	0.03	0.04	balance

The steel has a typical ferritic-pearlitic microstructure with carbon bulk inclusions, as shown in Figure 5a. Slow strain tensile tests were conducted on tubular specimens filled with hydrogen 5.0 at 70 bar, as well as nitrogen for reference.

Hydrogen reduces the elongation of fracture (EF) but does not have an effect on the yield and tensile strength, as demonstrated in Figure 5b. The impact of hydrogen embrittlement becomes noticeable at high strains, which is observed in many steels with low and average tensile strength compare also Figure 7. A better and more measurable parameter to assess the impact of hydrogen is the reduction of area (RA). In Figure 6 the fracture morphology in the scanning electron microscope (SEM) is shown.

FIGURE 5 a) Light microscope picture of the microstructure of vintage pipeline steel StE360 and b) stress-strain curve of tubular specimens of StE360 filled with pressurised hydrogen or nitrogen at 70 bars.

The fracture surfaces of the reference specimens exhibit an obvious necking and a ductile cup-and-cone fracture. In contrast, the hydrogen-tested specimens display a brittle fracture surface and do not exhibit a distinct necking. Nevertheless, the fracture morphology is typical for hydrogen-induced fracture in these materials [6–9]. The textbook brittle fracture surface with clearly visible grain boundaries and secondary cracks is not observed in all materials and under all conditions.

When comparing the material properties obtained from tubular and conventional specimens, it becomes evident that both techniques offer specific advantages, as results on 26 bcc steels with ferrite-pearlite, pearlite, bainite, or martensitic microstructures show. No changes in yield strength and tensile strength due to hydrogen are observed in both tubular and conventional specimens, compare Figure 7. However, the degree of necking is dependent on the specimen geometry and the test gas, compare Figure 8. In the reference atmosphere, conventional specimens exhibit greater necking than hydrogen-tested specimens. Conversely, for tubular specimens, those tested in hydrogen show more necking. This indicates that conventional specimens are more susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement, if the degree of necking is considered. Therefore, even minor changes in necking in tubular specimens may indicate hydrogen embrittlement. Comparable results with respect to tensile strength, yield strength, and necking behaviour are also published in [10] for austenitic steels 1.4301, 1.4305, 1.4306, 1.4404, 1.4408, and 1.4571. It is unknown whether this behaviour applies to high-strength steels, as no results on metallic materials with tensile strengths above 1200 MPa are currently available to compare tubular and conventional specimen. Unfortunately, a systematic analysis of the elongation of fracture on tubular and conventional specimen tests with hydrogen or reference gas is not done so far.

FIGURE 6 Scanning electron microscope pictures of the full fracture surface for (a) the reference specimen tested with nitrogen and (b) the specimen tested with hydrogen. Magnifications of the fracture morphology seen in the scanning electron microscope for (c) the reference specimen tested with nitrogen and (d) the specimen tested with hydrogen.

FIGURE 7 Comparison of the (a) yield strength (YS) and (b) ultimate tensile strength (UTS) of tubular specimens (TS) and conventional specimens (CS) for all 26 tested materials. Red dot = Test with hydrogen, Black dot = Reference test with pressurised nitrogen or with air.

FIGURE 8 Comparison of the reduction of area (RA) of conventional specimens (CS) and tubular specimens (TS) in tensile tests. Red dot = Test with hydrogen, Black dot = Reference test with pressurised nitrogen or with air.

A proposed reason for the divergent susceptibility for hydrogen embrittlement of tubular and conventional specimen could be the different supply of hydrogen, compare Figure 9.

For conventional specimens the position of highest stress, crack initiation and hydrogen supply are the very same position. Therefore, damage by necking and damage by hydrogen are in competition. Multiple cracks initiate on the outside and once a leading crack arises, this grows supported by hydrogen rather quickly, leading to an early fracture and reducing the possible necking, which is governed by plastic deformation. For tubular specimens the multiple cracks initiate on the inside, but necking start still form the outside. Especially in the early stages, the crack growth does not benefit from the stress increase of the necking. Therefore, necking and crack propagation appear parallel, giving the necking more time before the final fracture appears.

FIGURE 9 Schematic illustration of the proposed mechanisms of hydrogen damage in tensile test on (left) conventional specimen and (right) tubular specimen [10]

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The publication describes in detail the used setup for testing tubular specimen and addresses the safety aspects concerning explosive protection. The advantages of tubular specimens in comparison

to autoclaves are the lower invest costs especially due to lower safety concerns. Results of tensile tests on tubular specimen filled with hydrogen and on conventional specimens tested in the autoclave are compared for metallic materials with ultimate tensile strength up 1500 MPa. For a wide variety of ferritic and austenitic steel the yield strength and tensile strength are the same for conventional and tubular specimen. The results show that tubular specimens are a good alternative for tensile tests in the autoclave. However, the reduction of area of tubular specimen seems to be less sensitive for hydrogen embrittlement which must be respected when interpreting the results.

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

CS	Conventional Specimen
EF	Elongation of Fracture
RA	Reduction of Area
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
TS	Tubular Specimen
UTS	Ultimate Tensile Strength
YS	Yield Strength

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